

Preserving Memory

The creation and collapse of the Eastern Bloc – The Russian-Ukrainian war – The Hungarian Revolution of 1956 – Testimonies about life in the Eastern Bloc in the 1970s

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Table of contents

1. Brief overview of the creation of the Soviet bloc, its decline, the collapse of the USSR, and the causes of the Russian-Ukrainian war, the confrontation between the West and Russia, and the emergence of the desire for a multipolar world.
2. Brief overview of the events surrounding the Hungarian Revolution of 1956
3. Why collect testimonies from people who lived through these events in the 1970s?
 - 3.1. Methodological approach
 - 3.1.1. Target population, ages and countries of origin of participants
 - 3.1.2. Constitution of the target population
 - 3.2. Conditions for approaching the target population
 - 3.3. Selection of interviewees
4. Questions asked
5. Answers to the questions asked
6. Analysis of responses
7. Further reading

Extract

This article is divided into three parts:

The Eastern Bloc and the USSR, its collapse and the Russian-Ukrainian war -
The Hungarian revolution of 1956, the communist regime and the liberation of the USSR's
satellite countries from 1989 onwards - A collection of testimonies on daily life under the
socialist-communist regime during the 1970s.

In the aftermath of the Second World War, the Soviet Union, led by Joseph Stalin, took control of certain Eastern European and Central European countries to form the Eastern Bloc. In 1989, the Soviet Union's satellite countries decided to break free and in 1991, the USSR collapsed. From 1989 onwards, the satellite countries often made a brutal transition from communist rule to a market economy, which was not always well managed. Capitalism was a dream for many people, but disillusionment gradually replaced hopes for a better life for some. In the aftermath of 1989, many people were considered unproductive, such as the Roma

and the low-skilled, who were deemed unfit for work. Following the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989 and the collapse of the USSR in 1991, NATO welcomed most of Russia's former satellite countries, which were then in a weakened state. However, a certain Vladimir Putin came to power and reshuffled the deck by transforming Russia into a more competitive country and reorganizing the army. Meanwhile, the Balkan wars of the 1990s led to the break-up of Yugoslavia through the intervention of NATO, which had no international mandate from the UN.

In Ukraine, the "Maidan coup in Kiev (considered liberation by others) led to the removal from power in February 2014 of President Viktor Yanukovich, who was forced to flee the country. Yanukovich had refused to sign an association agreement with the European Union. Volodymyr Zelensky took power, promising to resolve the issues peacefully with Russia, which had become more powerful. Was this a gamble by Western countries to secure Ukraine, rich in black soil and rare minerals, which the European Union sorely lacks? Moscow has raised suspicions of Western intervention, including by the US. What was Europe, which lives only from trade and high-value-added product processing, lacking if not a country larger than France and rich in minerals? By cutting itself off from Russia to obey Uncle Sam while encompassing Ukraine, rich in minerals and rare earths, was this not a solution for Europe to find a new lease of life?

But little by little, the Russian-Ukrainian war has turned the world upside down: African countries are mistrustful of the West, and Russia's alliance with China, Iran and North Korea is becoming increasingly visible. The gradual disengagement of Third World countries from Western countries, the emergence of a multipolar world view that escapes the West, and the development of the BRICS countries are realities that have taken hold, creating an unexpected geopolitical earthquake for Westerners.

The future has become uncertain and the world dangerous, on the brink of a Third World war. This research also provides a brief overview of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution in order to understand what happened and to motivate this research, which aims to collect the words of 12 people about daily life in the 1970s. Indeed, it was a period of relative prosperity in Hungary under the yoke of the socialist-communist regime in the Eastern Bloc. What were the conditions of daily life in these countries? The testimonies of 12 people have provided a better understanding of their situation in everyday life. They also expressed their feelings about their experiences during this period and what they are currently experiencing.

1. Brief overview of the creation of the Soviet bloc, its decline, the collapse of the USSR, the Russian-Ukrainian war, the confrontation between the West and Russia, and the emergence of the desire for a multipolar world.

The Eastern Bloc was created in 1944. It consisted of communist regimes in countries under the control of the Soviet Union. In 1948, the Eastern Bloc was made up of the following countries: East Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia (consisting of the Czech Republic and Slovakia, which formed a single state), Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria and Albania.

The current Ukraine was part of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR), as well as the Baltic countries: Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.

Yugoslavia, led by Tito, was a collection of small regions integrated into the country called 'Yugoslavia'. Although Yugoslavia was a communist regime and had close ties with the USSR and the Eastern Bloc, it had managed to preserve a form of autonomy and independence from the USSR.

In 1989, the satellite countries of the USSR that made up the Eastern Bloc collapsed, with one major event in particular: the fall of the Berlin Wall separating East from West. A political (communist), economic and military alliance (the Warsaw Pact) strengthened the ties between the satellite countries and the USSR.

1991 was the official date of the implosion or collapse of the USSR, creating the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS). The following 15 states became independent following the collapse of the USSR: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan.

Russia is considered to be the successor state to the USSR. In 1990, the Baltic states demanded independence from the 15 states. The remaining 12 countries also seceded, forming the CIS, while joining the Collective Security Treaty Organisation.

In Ukraine, following the 'Maidan coup' in Kiev, which led to the unconstitutional removal from office of President Viktor Yanukovich in February 2014, the latter was forced to flee the country. Yanukovich had refused to sign an association agreement with the European Union. Volodymyr Zelensky took power, promising to resolve the issues peacefully with Russia, which had become a powerful neighbour.

However, Zelensky did not keep his promises, but followed the advice of certain Western leaders to oppose Russia and continue fighting the Russians who had invaded the country. Pogroms against the Russian-speaking population in Ukraine took place in the Donbass and Odessa, with hostilities escalating in 2014, prompting Russia to supply weapons to the dissident regions. Things got worse and on 24 February 2022, the conflict broke out on the orders of President Vladimir Putin, who sent troops into Ukraine for what he called "special operations".

Azov troops, considered by Russia to be neo-Nazi factions, are largely responsible for the pogroms. This dramatic situation led to Russia's invasion of Ukraine. The removal of the legitimately elected president, the Maidan coup, Ukraine's formal request to join the European Economic Community and NATO, and the pogroms against Russian speakers left Russia with no choice, as it absolutely did not want the West to reach its borders. For the Western camp, on the other hand, Maidan is synonymous with freedom for the Ukrainian people.

A certain mistrust of NATO was generated by the fact that NATO, in the 1990s, without a mandate from the United Nations (UN), attacked Serbia and is primarily responsible for the break-up of Yugoslavia.

Need we also recall the 'Minsk Agreements' of 2014-2015, which guaranteed peace?

The words of Angela Merkel and François Hollande have exposed the manoeuvres to stop Russia's advance in the face of a Ukraine that is running out of steam. In 'Le monde en

devenir' (The world in the making), a strategic column published on Friday 6 January 2023, we read the following:

"Following Angela Merkel's admission on 7 December, former President François Hollande, who was alongside the German Chancellor during the negotiations for the Minsk agreements in 2015-2015, also admitted that the agreements were not intended to guarantee peace, but to allow the Kiev regime to "buy time" and rearm.

For President Vladimir Putin, this deception on the part of the West was unacceptable; moreover, the aim was to weaken Russia by using Ukraine, hence the idea of a proxy armed conflict. The West would therefore have provoked a fratricidal war to weaken Russia. As a reminder, the Minsk agreements (8 December 1991, but subsequently contested) confirmed the break-up of the Soviet Union, giving rise to the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS).

The "Minsk Protocol signed on 5 December 2014 is an agreement aimed at ending the war in Donbass. A ceasefire protocol concerning the Donbass region (Minsk II) was signed on 11 February 2015 following the failure of the 2014 Minsk agreement. Under the auspices of the Organisation for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), the participants in the Minsk II summit brought together the leaders of the following countries: Russia, Ukraine, France and Germany – The Donetsk and Luhansk regions.

The aim was to agree on measures concerning the war in Donbass.

According to President Vladimir Putin, the Minsk agreements were merely a pretext for Ukraine to rearm with the help of Western countries. The breakdown of the Minsk protocol was formalized by Russia's official recognition of the independence of the Donetsk and Luhansk People's Republics on 21 February 2022.

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'Bitter Ukrainian defeat in Debaltseve', *Le Temps*, 18 February 2015, ISSN 1423-3967

After the break-up of the USSR, Russia considered it intolerable that the Atlantic Alliance (NATO) should come to Russia's borders. With the Minsk agreements flouted, the Russian-Ukrainian war increasingly became a proxy war, with the main suppliers of arms to Ukraine being the United States under President Biden and the Western world, against Russia.

The Western world undoubtedly believed it could bring Russia to its knees, and perhaps even dismantle it, through the weapons supplied to the Ukrainian army and more than 17,000 economic sanctions, as well as by paralysing bank transfers through Russia's withdrawal from the SWIFT banking system. In addition, the West had frozen more than \$300 billion in Russian assets to undermine Russian objectives. This freezing of Russian assets had a

destabilizing effect on Asian countries and many countries in South America and Africa. Unfortunately for the West, Russia was able to find other trading partners such as China, India, etc. This Russian momentum prevented the West from achieving its goals. The reality on the ground and the global upheaval overwhelmed the West, which was trying to go all in, having invested billions in this war with little to show for it. Unfortunately, misjudgements and poor strategic choices have meant that it is the people of Western countries who are still paying the price today, seeing their purchasing power decline. The precariousness is increasing as the cost of basic consumer goods rises. Sanctions against Russia also seem to be having a boomerang effect, hitting people in their wallets.

But why are Western countries, including the US, making such efforts to weaken and, at best, dismantle Russia? Why so much effort to defend Ukraine, where corruption is rife? A Ukraine accused of harbouring neo-Nazi factions in its army?

Hasn't the Russia-Ukraine war gradually become a quasi-direct confrontation, given the military advisers and instructors present on Ukrainian soil? Wasn't it a gamble by Western countries to bring Ukraine, rich in black soil and rare minerals, into their fold? Which the European Union sorely lacks? The sending of weapons in abundance during President Joe Biden's administration and Europe's increasing commitment to breaking Russia are undoubtedly an answer to that question. What is Europe, which lives only from trade and the transformation of high-value-added products, lacking if not a country larger than France and overflowing with minerals? By cutting itself off from Russia to obey Uncle Sam, while encompassing Ukraine, rich in minerals and rare earths, wasn't this a solution for Europe to bounce back economically?

But the tide has turned and, against all expectations and to the great despair of the European Union, it is former President Donald Trump who has returned to the presidency, not Joe Biden, who withdrew from the race in favour of Kamala Harris, who was soundly defeated! In the adventure, President Trump has not forgotten Europe's hostility towards him. It was therefore predictable that President Trump would disengage from this Russian-Ukrainian war, which concerns his predecessor and the EU more than him. After hundreds of billions of pounds in arms given by the West to a Ukraine where corruption is rife, and to no avail, Europe has continued to support Ukraine. But why continue if the cause is lost when Russia continues to show its strength and Ukraine its weakness?

It is true that for Europe, the prospect of losing Ukraine would be a bitter defeat that would be difficult to explain to Europeans, who are increasingly tightening their belts because of the costs of this war for Europe. If defeat were confirmed, the fate of Europe would be bleak. Let us hope that the blind rush forward of certain leaders will not lead us into a Third World war.

But for the US, things are not so simple, because the rapprochement between Russia and China is worrying. In theory, isn't it advantageous to bring down Russia so that the only enemy left is China and a global world led by the West can be achieved?

And as for African countries, gaining greater independence and escaping Western influence has been the main reason for rejecting the West, the former colonial power. Indeed, the Russian-Ukrainian conflict has opened Pandora's box: the possibility of getting rid of Western neocolonialism by moving closer to Russia and China. Is this a new hope for the Global South to break free and take control of its own destiny? France, in particular, has lost a lot in the affair, having been ejected by several African countries. The world order has begun to falter,

something that Westerners do not seem to have foreseen. Did the predecessor of the current president of the United States misjudge the forces at play and the catastrophic outcome of this war? Was Europe blind to follow certain warmongers? Could peace not have been achieved in Istanbul if the President of Ukraine had not listened to his warmongering supporters? In any case, is there not a risk that the history of this war will end with the tragic conclusion: ‘All dead for nothing’?

Is there not a risk that responsibility will be diluted, with a few scapegoats being found to act as a smokescreen? Are the people of the EU not at risk of paying a heavy price for a war they did not choose? Why is Hungary the only country that has had the courage to opt for popular consultations? Ultimately, has the Europe of our fathers, who sought common prosperity in peace, been betrayed by the EU's current choices? Does the resolute globalist EU not have a duty to consult the people about their future?

The Russian-Ukrainian war seems to have created several easily observable factors:

- Mistrust of Western countries on the part of African and Asian countries.
- Certain South American countries, such as Brazil, which is a giant in terms of population and economy, have taken a pro-Russian stance.
- The desire for economic independence among African countries (Global South) and the Third World.
- A gradually emerging alliance between Russia, China, Iran and North Korea.
- The gradual disengagement of certain Third World countries from Western countries.
- India, which has not forgotten its colonial past with Great Britain, continues to trade with Russia despite Western sanctions.
- The gradual rapprochement between Russia and China, so feared by the West in geopolitical and economic terms, is becoming an alliance.
- Opposing visions between South Africa and Western countries.
- The emergence of a multipolar world view that eludes Westerners.
- The development of the BRICS countries expanded to include other important countries such as Egypt and Saudi Arabia are becoming a major economic competitor for the G7.
- The ‘de-dollarisation’ of the world is underway, with Russia and China as the main players, and India and other countries seeming to follow suit.
- The emergence of ‘sovereignists’ opposed to the “globalist” project of Western countries.
- The ‘double standards’ policy, often used by the West, is considered hypocritical and unfair.
- South Africa denounces the ‘double standards’ policy and shows the way forward in a new world order.
- New trade alliances are escaping the power of the West, such as the Mercosur agreement between Brazil and the European Economic Community.
- The weakness created by the EU cutting itself off from Russian gas, which, unable to obtain cheap energy, is seeing its economic decline.
- Russia seems less isolated than Western countries, which seem unable to find a way out of the situation for which they are largely responsible.
- Asian, Middle Eastern, North African and other countries have not forgotten the organized coups or dubious interventions without a UN mandate, such as the wars in

Iraq, Syria, Libya, Afghanistan, etc. Westerners do not seem to have a good press in these countries.

- Asian countries want to free themselves from the dollar, with China seeming to be leading the way.
- The catastrophic demographics of Western countries do not seem to be offset by migration, which, if poorly managed, creates more and more social unrest.
- The freezing of Russian assets is an unprecedented move, undermining the rest of the world's confidence in the West.

Western countries, once colonizers and 'world police' until now, are becoming a weakened bloc, with an undeniable human factor: low population growth.

The West is becoming a large minority: 1 billion inhabitants compared to 7 billion, out of a global population of 8.062 billion in 2023. It is undoubtedly possible that the world order could be overturned by alliances in Asian countries, drawing in other countries from the rest of the world. Contrary to all expectations, it is not Russia that is isolated, but increasingly the Western bloc. Have we gone too far? Is this a point of no return? Only time will tell. As Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orbán keeps saying, 'diplomacy is the only option' that can get us out of this mess, not war. Redefining healthy political and trade relations is the only way to build trust. Good relations require a 'win-win' trade perspective. This implies truly sovereign states, thus ruling out 'globalism'.

Given that fertility rates in Africa are very high compared to Western countries, where they are dangerously low, this could lead to significant migration problems if migration is poorly managed in terms of reception and without a real integration policy. Poorly managed migration can lead to destabilization and an even greater risk of marginalization in Western countries.

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2. Brief overview of events surrounding the Hungarian Revolution of 1956

At the end of the Second World War, in 1944-45, the Russians joined forces with the Americans and their allies in Berlin. This situation led to the division of Germany into two parts, with a wall erected in Berlin between the Western forces and the Russian forces. Russia

and the United States, the great victors of the war against Hitler's Nazi Germany, divided Europe in two; the Russians took the Eastern European countries and some Central European countries: East Germany, Poland, Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria and Albania, which became 'satellite countries' of the USSR. The three Baltic countries, Lithuania, Estonia and Latvia, were incorporated into the USSR. The Warsaw Pact was created on 14 May 1955, uniting the satellite countries politically, economically and militarily with the USSR. This pact was a symmetrical response to NATO. The Warsaw Pact was dissolved on 1 July 1991, preceding the dissolution of the USSR in 1991.

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Matyàs Ràkosi, alias Màyàs Rosenfeld (1892-1971) took power in Hungary from 1948 to 1956. He was the first president of the Council of Ministers, then became Prime Minister of the Republic of Hungary in 1953-1953. He was responsible for purges, imprisonment and political liquidations. Anti-Semitism flourished under and after Ràkosi's regime, even though he himself was of Jewish origin. Following his arrival in power, Khrushchev forced him to resign and go into exile in the USSR. Ràkosi made the mistake of following the Stalinist line and the cult of personality, which had been banned by Khrushchev. He joined Joseph Stalin's anti-Semitic campaign in 1953. His 'salami technique' consisted of eliminating from power anything that was not communist: the Church, political parties, dissidents and opponents of the regime. His successor was Imre Nagy, born in 1896 and summarily executed in 1958 along with another architect of the 1956 Hungarian Revolution, Péter Maléter, who was also executed.

Dating of the Hungarian Revolution of 1956: 23 October 1956 to 10 November 1956.

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The Hungarian uprising was a popular revolt largely initiated by students against the Hungarian communist regime and its policies imposed by the USSR. The Stalinist regime had

become intolerable for the population due to constant repression. Added to this were the major economic difficulties Hungary was experiencing in 1956.

Censorship and the secret police, known as the AVH (államvédelmi hatóság), acted brutally, imprisoning, torturing and killing opponents of the regime. One of the most notorious prisons at the time was in Recsk, which was referred to as a 'labour camp' (1950-1953), but in reality it was a 'Hungarian Gulag'. Other sordid places still existed in 1956 where torture and liquidation were practised. The spark that ignited the powder keg came when the secret police (AVH) began firing on the crowd in Budapest.

In 1956, the economic crisis was severe, and it should be noted that a significant portion of agricultural and industrial production was sent from satellite countries to the USSR.

During the 1956 Revolution, Prime Minister Imre Nagy decided to withdraw from the Warsaw Pact. This was the last straw for Nikita Khrushchev, who ordered the revolt to be crushed. Soviet troops (around 200,000 soldiers) invaded the country and entered Budapest on 4 November 1956.

Kádár János (1912-1989) arrived on 7 November 1956 with a convoy of Soviet tanks. He was installed by the USSR to rule the country. He announced the formation of the 'Revolutionary Workers' and Peasants' Government' (Magyar Forradalmi Munkás-Paraszt Kormány). He led the People's Republic of Hungary until 1988.

Alongside repression, torture of opponents and purges, Kádár attempted to liberalize the country somewhat. For example, he eased religious repression and allowed, under strict control, a certain degree of political dissent, giving the country a somewhat democratic image. He even decriminalized homosexuality in 1961. Unlike his predecessor Rákosi, he rejected anti-Semitic policies. Under his regime, it is true that Hungary offered better living conditions than most other countries in the Eastern Bloc.

Thus, Russian troops arrived in Budapest with tanks. According to renowned historian Mária Schmidt (Hu), the invasion was carried out by Soviet troops, but also with Ukrainian soldiers. She replied to John Cleese as follows: 'The invasion was carried out by Soviet troops, including Ukrainians...'.

But why did the West not respond to Hungary's request for help in 1956?

Péter Szijjártó, Minister of Foreign Affairs of the current Hungarian Government, recently stated the following: "... In 1956, during the Hungarian Revolution, the Hungarians asked the West for help, but in vain...

Finally, how many victims did the Revolution claim?

Approximately 2,500 killed

13,000 wounded approximately

More than 200,000 people fled the communist regime. The two main routes out of the country were Austria and Tito's Yugoslavia.

Mass emigration took place between November 1956 and March 1957.

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3. Why collect testimonies from people who lived through the events of 1956?

Much has been written about the Hungarian uprising and revolution of 1956, but there have not been many collections of testimonies from people who lived through the period between 1945 and 1989. I wanted to fill this gap by going into the field to ask people about their experiences during this period, and more specifically during what is considered to be the most prosperous period: the 1970s. What were the conditions of daily life? What do they think of their current situation?

I believe it is important to preserve their memory, given that this target population was between 25 and 30 years old in 1975, meaning they were born between 1945 and 1950. These are people who can recount their experiences first-hand. In 2024, these people will be between 74 and 79 years old.

3.1. Methodological approach

This research project is focused on qualitative analysis, with analysis of the target population's statements.

3.1.1. Target population, ages and countries of origin

Twelve people born between 1945 and 1950.

Six people (three men and three women) from Hungary, including:

Two in Budapest, two in Szászvár and two in Komló

Two people (one man and one woman) from Slovakia (Kosice)

2 people (1 man and 1 woman) from Romania (Satu Mare)

2 people (1 man and 1 woman) from Serbia (Subotica)

3.1.2. Composition of the target population

The target individuals who agreed to be interviewed are currently aged between 74 and 79.

3.2. Conditions for approaching the target population

All individuals had Hungarian as their mother tongue and lived either in Hungary or in a region with a significant Hungarian minority (> 10%).

3.3. Selection of interviewees

Gender parity was respected in order to obtain a wider range of information.

Anonymity had to be respected at the request of the participants. Only the initials of the individuals are mentioned, along with their gender and age.

4. Questions asked

Can you describe daily life in the 1970s and the importance of the family? Do you feel nostalgic for the old regime? Is it better now? What form of censorship did you notice during this period? Can you tell me about the school system? The culture? Religious freedom? Were people suspicious of each other? Can you talk about the school system, the culture, religious freedom? What do you think of your current situation?

Note: During the conversation, forgotten questions were revisited.

5. Answers to the questions asked (translation from Hungarian)

Can you describe daily life in the 1970s and the importance of the family? Are you nostalgic for the old regime?

Is it better now? What forms of censorship did you notice during that period?

Can you tell me about the school system? About culture? About religious freedom? Were people suspicious of each other? Can you talk about the school system, culture, religious freedom? What do you think of your current situation?

Hungary, Budapest, Witness 1, Female, 74;0

Under the Kàdàr regime, I have to say it was better, when I hear what my parents say about Ràkosi, with him it was terrible, people were arrested for the slightest thing, they were imprisoned, tortured. In the 1970s, we had enough to eat and life was fairly comfortable. People went to restaurants several times a week and there was gypsy music in many restaurants. Heating, electricity and water were very cheap. School was free, as was healthcare. But you still had to give something under the table to get good service.

In the countryside, I remember my aunt bringing fruit and eggs. Others brought meat or money. We had a work book that was often checked. Not going to work was severely

punished by the police. Everyone was afraid of the police. The hardest thing was leaving the country to go to Austria to see a cousin who had fled in 1956. People knew each other and knew whom they could talk to openly without getting into trouble with the police or the authorities. That said, nothing was completely safe, because there could always be a “brick” around the corner. Bricks were spies, informers.

Culturally, it was a rich period, because folklore was quite vibrant, unlike today, and music was everywhere. But now there's a renewed interest in all that. Ultimately, what I'm nostalgic for about that period is the closeness between people, the mutual support, and families that were less fragmented than they are today. What's better now is that there's more freedom to say what you think... sometimes even too much. The cities and countryside were much cleaner. Nowadays, people are more isolated. There are ways to get rich, but not for many. I don't really know how to choose between the past and the present.

Budapest, Witness 2, Male, 75;0

I have mixed feelings, actually. For example, I had to wait nearly five years to get my Trabant, and there was very little choice. Yes, there was the two-stroke Wartburg, but it didn't run well. The Skoda was better, but to stabilize the car, there was a round concrete block in the back. The Trabant from East Germany was in high demand because it could get through anywhere easily.

I wasn't able to go to university because I wasn't accepted. In my opinion, it was because I didn't come from a working-class background. I became a mechanic. School was free, but often young people didn't have a choice. The authorities probably had a say in the choices. I had three children and we had to live in a 61m² flat, which isn't much, but it was really cheap. Food was cheap, as were books. But in many shops, you often had to queue. Food and other products were often in short supply and you often heard people say, “There's no more”.

Having a party card opened doors. Most people had a party card, but, in my opinion, they didn't believe in it. Otherwise, it was easy to get food and clothes, even if the choice was limited. When a foreigner from the West came with their car, everyone would look at the car and take photos. Many people thought that life in the West must be paradise. What I liked about the old regime was that if you were ill, after a check-up, they left you alone, unlike now. If you were ill, you were treated for free. School was free. You had more friends because people were more supportive.

There was censorship, yes, but if you didn't rock the boat and you had your party card, you could live in peace. Nowadays, it's a more savage capitalist system, a colder system: you work, you eat; you don't have a job, you die. For me, it was better and safer before, even if you had to be careful with your spending. Although today, both husband and wife have to work to make ends meet and not have to be too careful with their spending.

Hungary, Szászvár, Witness 3, Woman, 76;0

I worked as a nursery school teacher. The school has always had to be clean and every year we repaired and repainted whatever needed doing. Life wasn't so bad compared to neighbouring countries like Romania or Czechoslovakia (now two countries). Censorship was real. The state was responsible for the curriculum and every year, pupils received their textbooks free of charge. But the authors were chosen: either Hungarian author accepted by the state or Russian authors. At the time, there weren't many advertising posters.

Travelling by bus, tram or train was cheap, unlike today. The extended family, including grandparents, aunts and uncles, saw each other often. Family and social life was richer than it is now. There was never a shortage of food, either because of family solidarity or because in the countryside everyone raised pigs, chickens, vegetables, etc. If money allowed people to buy or sell, it was not uncommon for them to barter.

In terms of education, everything went fairly well except for many Roma whose parents were illiterate and whose children did not attend school regularly. The authorities intervened promptly, but Roma children generally had many learning difficulties and many of them ended up in special schools for children with learning difficulties. In terms of work, there was work for everyone in the coal mine, even for those who were underqualified.

The Roma were often underqualified, but they were put to work, even if it meant five or six people sweeping when two would have been enough. Censorship? It was more prevalent in the cities than in the countryside, although you had to be careful. Russian was compulsory for older children, but Hungarians didn't like the Russian language very much and sometimes the teacher was understanding. Being rich? That was impossible. You could have a house or an apartment.

The wealthiest also had a second home, but often it was just a small house of 25 to 40 square metres. Of course, I know that the apparatchiks lived in greater luxury, but it was taboo to talk about it. Religious censorship was more prevalent in the cities than in the countryside, I think. Here in the countryside, I was always able to go to church without any problems, but I also had my party card. I think the authorities were more tolerant than under Rákosi... a nasty piece of work! A Jew who didn't like Jews... Can you understand that? Kádár showed more flexibility; he worked for the good of the people. In fact, the Romanians and others envied our living conditions.

Szászvár, Witness 4, Male, 78;0

I worked in the mine, but it closed in the 1980s. Why? I don't know, because I know there's still a lot of coal there. In the 1980s, you could feel that the tide was turning, that the regime was running out of steam. Prices were starting to rise, but people were still surprised by what happened in 1989.

I think life was easier and more peaceful before. We had to work, everything was very controlled. When the work was done, you had to pretend to work and everything was fine. Now it's not like that, it's not as good and you have to produce, produce, produce. I wouldn't want to be 30 now.

My miner's pension doesn't allow me to make ends meet, so I bought a small plot of land where I grow potatoes and vegetables. I used to live in an apartment, but I sold it to buy a small house with a garden to get by... as long as I'm in good health!

As for religion, I know that in some places there was pressure from the authorities, but not in Szàszvár. It must be said that in the Baranya region, there are many people of Swabian origin (Schwabens) who are very attached to the Evangelical Church. What I regret is the gradual loss of village traditions and folklore.

People used to talk to each other more. Now, there are neighbours who don't even know each other. Even in greater poverty, solidarity used to enable people to get by. Not now, if you're poor.

Hungary, Komlo, Witness 5, female, 77;0

(In Hungary, primary school lasts eight years and secondary school (Gimnàzium) lasts four years)

I am from Komlo, a town that was thriving at the time, built from scratch to be an industrial town with coal mines.

We are Gypsies, but proud of it. We had five children. Unfortunately, we couldn't help them because we are illiterate. It must be said that our children were quite discriminated against at school, like other Gypsy children. Yet there are many Gypsy families in Komlo. Three of our children went to a school for children with learning difficulties. The other two managed to finish eighth grade but had to go to vocational school. One of them became a bricklayer and the other has no qualifications. But I don't think things are better today, even though the government is making an effort and we are represented.

Life was better before because we had worked. My husband died five years ago. He was a miner and learned the trade on the job. He worked in coal mining, but he contracted a miner's disease and had trouble breathing. He was retired at 50. He was a talented viola player and played in a small orchestra of four or five musicians who performed in restaurants. He earned quite a lot of money. Now all that's over and it's only in Budapest and a few other big cities where highly skilled Gypsies still play in a few places, mainly for tourists.

We lived well in Komlo, we didn't skimp on heating, electricity or water. Now? It's a massacre for the wallet. The food was good, cheap and we could dress properly. We never left Hungary, not even for tourism... What for? So people could look at us funny? I know that because one of my cousins' lives in Vienna, Austria... And then life became very expensive. Yes, I liked it better before. There was a lot of censorship after the Second World War. We were settled and assimilated by force.

Today's Gypsies no longer live like our grandparents or great-grandparents, who could still live in caravans. The communist regime abolished all that, probably because it considered our way of life medieval. Culture? Gypsy culture has lost much of its value and traditions, and the

language is gradually being lost among young people. As for religion, we were never said anything. But beware, under the Rákosi regime, Gypsies and Jews trembled with fear of being imprisoned or arrested... The secret police (AVH) were not kind, according to what our parents said. Life today has become less humane, I think.

Komlo, Witness 6, male, 76

‘Regime change’ in 1989

Daily life consisted of going to work very early in the morning, working and coming home quite late, eating and going to bed. Only on Sundays could people really relax socially and think about something other than work. But apart from that, almost everything was free: school for the children, healthcare, even if you had to pay a small amount for the doctor, rent was cheap, food was cheap... And as long as you kept quiet and the police didn't come, you could sleep peacefully. You could even drink a little during work from time to time, and the boss would offer us a drink. I worked as a farm labourer all my life.

When I was younger, I thought my pension would be enough, but with the “renszerváltás” in 1989, savage capitalism came and turned everything upside down. And it's certainly no better for people of my generation. Except for the powerful, who knew how to divide the pie among themselves, but not the little people. It's crazy to think that it was the socialists and communists who seemed to be the most fervent supporters of the regime who turned their coats and started praising capitalism. Many of them lined their pockets between 1989 and 1992. High-ranking military officers were granted pensions that were astronomical (four to six times higher) compared to the rest of the population. Former politicians from the old regime switched to liberal politics on the left or right. There are even some ‘bricks’ and AVH members who have risen to important positions. For example, Prime Minister Horn Gyula, who was an AVH agent, i.e. a member of the secret police who could interrogate or torture people.

I prefer life now, even if it is unfair and difficult. Yes, there was censorship, even under Kàdàr, who kept a discreet watch... Everyone was watched and it was essential not to demonstrate against the regime!

But is it better now, with prices skyrocketing? A Europe that increasingly resembles a socialist-communist regime? What will become of us tomorrow? I fear for my children and grandchildren.

Slovakia, Kosice, Witness 7, female, 75 years old

Life was hard before, but we were used to it. There were small village festivals, folk festivals, tea dances, etc. The theatre was cheap, as was transport. Energy was cheap too. But we had to live in a cramped house for a family of five. Human relationships were more direct and people were willing to help, unlike now... it's more of a selfish world.

In the past, the Hungarian minority did not suffer any discrimination. Nowadays, there are places in the country where discrimination exists, not only against Gypsies, but also against Hungarians. People didn't seem to be in a hurry or stressed, whereas now I see the opposite. We certainly lived poorly, but differently, and we could get by, whereas now it's difficult to make ends meet!

Culture and folklore, dancing and singing were part of everyday life, whereas now all that seems to have disappeared, or at least diminished. Now, if I didn't have my little flat, I wouldn't be able to live on the pension I receive.

For me, it was better before. As far as censorship was concerned, anyone who didn't oppose the regime or get involved in politics and led a normal, peaceful life was left alone. In the past, young people without qualifications could find work; now it's very difficult.

Kosice, Witness 8, Male, 74;0

I worked as an arc welder in a factory. I learned on the job because I was given the opportunity to do so. Nowadays, I don't think I would have that chance. Now you have to work hard to find a job. Worse than that, there are university graduates doing the work of office clerks who, back then, had only finished secondary school or even less.

Life today is stressful and fast paced. I see this with my two children, who have completed their university studies. They are always under pressure and stressed. What about everyday life? We lived more simply, of course, but life was cheaper and we could afford to go out to a restaurant at the weekend and enjoy live music. Now, going to a restaurant is a luxury, even without live music. Going to concerts was normal. Going to the theatre was also affordable. Nowadays, the prices are too high for me.

I remember that back then, even grandparents went to the theatre, to concerts and to restaurants. I really thought that 1989 would be a lucky year, but I've been singing a different tune for the last ten years. With the war in Ukraine on top of everything else, prices are rising... it's no longer sustainable. We're not even asked for our opinion on this war. In a war, it's always the same: those in power risks much less than the people who are used as cannon fodder!

Especially money to neo-Nazis, that's the last straw! For me, it was better before, even if it was a fairly authoritarian communist regime.

Serbia, Subotica, Witness 9, Female, 76;0

In Tito's Yugoslavia, there wasn't the mess there is now. People didn't hate each other. I think NATO is the troublemaker. They bombed my country. The Serbs will never forget that. On top of that, life is becoming too expensive. It's getting harder and harder for my children to get by. I help them as much as I can, but it's difficult. My husband died three years ago. I still grow my own vegetables because fruit and vegetables are expensive.

Life in Yugoslavia? We had everything! Mountains, the sea, a good climate, and people didn't fight each other under Tito.

It took those idiots from France, England, and America to come and destroy it. Is it better now? No! Everything is expensive, including meat. Travel is expensive, and when we go to the new country next door, we're treated like foreigners.

Under Tito, there was undoubtedly censorship, but we could still express ourselves... Now, I don't know... I wouldn't dare say what I think about a lot of things, because I'd probably get into trouble with some shitty association or other. The Hungarian minority? There have been clashes and ups and downs! Now things have calmed down with the current government.

Living conditions were better than they are now, in my opinion. I hope Serbia doesn't make the mistake of losing its sovereignty by becoming a member of a union of corrupt dictators.

The Westerners tore my country apart, but God will punish them! That's all I have to say.

Subotica, Witness 10, Male, 78;0

My wife is ill, she has Alzheimer's, and her care is expensive. I have two children, each with two children, a girl and a boy. It's difficult for them. Daily life was easier before than it is now. We were lucky not to be under the thumb of the USSR, even though we had good relations with them. We lived better than the Romanians, for example. The Hungarians had roughly the same standard of living as us in the 1970s. I know because I have a family on both sides.

Food was cheap, as was clothing. School was free for children. Healthcare was good enough and inexpensive. Now it's different. Yes, I miss that period of my life. People were calmer and there were fewer conflicts.

The war in the 1990s ravaged the country and divided it. Was that a good solution? No! Look at it now! There's Serbia, then the Serbs in Bosnia, Kosovo... I'm afraid the West did more harm than good by intervening.

I used to like going to the cinema and concerts, but now I'm old and can't afford it! Culturally, too, things have changed a lot... Young people only listen to English songs and traditions are being lost.

Romania, Satu Mare, Witness 11, Female, 77;0

I was a housewife and did a lot of gardening to keep our expenses down. Ceaușescu's Romania and his Securitate henchmen? It was shit!

Life was difficult. We lived off our small plot of land, our chickens and our pigs. It's true that water wasn't expensive, nor was wine, but we also had vineyards. Being Hungarian, I couldn't speak Hungarian to the shopkeepers. They were forbidden to speak their mother tongue.

Ceaușescu did everything he could to disperse the Hungarian population in the towns and villages... What a piece of shit! Before, there were about 2.5 million of us... Now there are about 1.5 million. Currently, there are ups and downs, but the nationalists hate us. Some of them tell us outright, “This is our land! Go back to Hungary!”

In the 1970s? It was better than in the 1960s or 1980s. However, life was cheaper in Hungary and there were more products to buy. We used to go there to shop because here it was really a dictatorship with the cult of personality surrounding Ceaușescu. School was free, yes, but there weren't any schools everywhere.

I wouldn't want to go back to the past, even if life is difficult here. We joined Europe, but what for? We don't have any more food on our plates. Europe is an opportunity for the rich and influential, but not for the population.

Censorship? It was practised on a daily basis. Everyone was afraid of everyone else because the Securitate had ears everywhere. Opponents? They were made to disappear without any problem. We have two children and three grandchildren; they plan to leave the country. They see no future here and wages are very low! Why are there such differences in wages in Europe? Are we second-class Europeans?

Culture and folklore were quite vibrant in the 1970s, but not any more, which is a shame. We will die here because we are too old to leave.

Satumare, Witness 12, Male, 74;0

I worked as a warehouse worker, then in a wood-cutting factory. Life was hard and there was a shortage of everything, even if you had money to buy things. We had to go to Debrecen in Hungary because there was more to buy there. Life was harder here.

Censorship affected religion and political opinions. We had to be discreet because the secret police (Securitate) were everywhere. The apparatchiks of the dictator Ceaușescu lived well, but not the population, who were dying from overwork and lack of basic necessities. We had to queue to buy things and the shop shelves were often empty. I don't regret that the regime collapsed along with its dictator. What's a shame is that the former apparatchiks were able to change sides and position themselves politically after 1989! But as my father used to say, rotting shit makes good carrots grow. But while that may be true in nature, I'm not so sure about humans.

The situation for young people is often hopeless, and the only solution is to hope to find something better elsewhere. But I don't know if that's a good solution. In any case, Europe has invested in our country, draining our wealth, but what do people get in return? I don't see anything coming, anyway.

6. Analysis of responses

Responses to the questions are mixed, but a majority seem to say that, although conditions were difficult in the past, the quality of life was better.

In Romania, on the other hand, there is no nostalgia, unlike among people living in Serbia.

In Hungary, although opinions are mixed, those questioned say that there were positive aspects to living conditions in the 1970s.

In Romania, there is still a lot of resentment towards the Ceaușescu regime; living conditions seemed miserable.

In Hungary, however, this resentment does not seem to have existed, except among the generation of parents who experienced the dark regime of Ràkosi.

Kàdàr is seen as the man who reached a compromise with the USSR to offer Hungarians a certain standard of living.

In present-day Slovakia, although the responses are mixed, people feel that life today is very difficult compared to 1970.

Several people questioned denounced the fact that their daily lives are not necessarily better since joining the EU.

Finally, Serbs denounced the illegal bombing of their country by NATO forces, which they believe has created chaos.

Censorship was discreet in Hungary and apparently virulent in Romania.

In Slovakia and Yugoslavia, censorship existed but was not as strong as in Romania.

Some respondents said that discrimination against minorities was rare in the 1970s, particularly in Yugoslavia and Slovakia.

However, the Roma appear to have been discriminated against, especially in Romania and Slovakia.

The Russian-Ukrainian war seems to be a concern for those interviewed, with some very strong criticism of Western intervention in the conflict and the corruption prevailing in Ukraine.

I will leave it to the reader to explore the interviewees' comments in greater depth.

This research should be considered a preliminary investigation, but it has the merit of encouraging readers to question themselves and want to learn more about the subject.

I would like to thank the participants for their sincere answers to the questions.

7. Further reading

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